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**Leucoanthocyanidins from *Saraca asoca*
Stem Bark**

J. KAUR DUGGAL and K. MISRA

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002

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S. asoca (Ashoka : N. O. Leguminosae) is well known for its medicinal properties. Its highly astringent stem bark is used in uterine affections in menorrhagia and scorpion sting¹. In the past, some chemical constituents have been reported to be present in this bark^{2,3,4}. The bark was extracted with acetone at room temperature and the concentrated viscous mass was subsequently macerated with petroleum ether, ethyl acetate, acetone and methanol respectively.

The light petroleum extracted some waxy matter along with β -sitosterol. The ethylacetate extract on fractional precipitation with light petrol yielded a homogeneous compound (A). The acetone fraction on column chromatography on silica gel afforded compound (B), methanol fraction on repeated crystallisation with methanol-ethyl acetate yielded a homogeneous entity (C).

From a study of colour reactions, UV spectral data, acid hydrolysis, degradation, co-chromatography, mp, mmp compound (A) C₂₁H₂₄O₁₁ was identified as leucopelargonidin 3-O- β -D-glucoside by the well known procedure^{5,6}. Compound (B) C₁₅H₁₄O₆ was found to be identical with leucopelargonidin⁷ and compound (C) C₁₅H₁₄O₇ with leucocyanidin⁷.

The high astringency of the bark can be ascribed to the presence of these flavan-diols, and to the highly water soluble glycoside.

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**Studies on Heterocyclic Primary Amines. III :
Synthesis of N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)
Triphenyl Imidophosphoranes**

M. EL-DEEK, E. EL-SAWI and K. EL-BADRY

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science and University
College for Women, Ain-Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

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IMIDOPHOSPHORANES in which the nitrogen atom is attached to heterocyclic ring are rare. Because of the increasing biological¹⁻⁶ and industrial⁷ uses of 1,3,4-oxadiazole derivatives, we became interested in the preparation of new types of 1,3,4-oxadiazolylimidophosphoranes(I).

(I)

Ar

a = C₆H₅, b = *m*-ClC₆H₄, c = *p*-ClC₆H₄,
d = *p*-CH₃C₆H₄, e = *p*-CH₃OC₆H₄

The synthetic route which was found to be most convenient for the desired heterocyclic imidophosphoranes(I) employed the method of Horner and Oediger⁸. Thus, on subjecting 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole to dibromotriphenylphosphorane in dry benzene in the presence of triethylamine, at room temperature followed by four hours' reflux under nitrogen, the desired imidophosphoranes(I) were obtained in 70-80% yield.

The i.r. spectra of all the compounds(I) showed a band at about 1300 cm⁻¹ due to the N=P stretching vibration^{9a} with the concomitant disappearance of the NH stretching vibration at 3140 cm⁻¹ present in the starting aminooxadiazoles. The P-C (aromatic) stretching absorption was observed for all the compounds at 1440 cm⁻¹^{9b}. The i.r. spectra of all the compounds(I) also showed the cyclic C=N stretching bands at 1640-1690 cm⁻¹.

The structure of the imidophosphoranes was further confirmed by hydrolysis. When compounds (I) were refluxed with dilute HCl for three hours, gave the parent aminooxadiazole hydrochloride and triphenylphosphine oxide, identified by mixed m.p. and comparison of the i.r. with an authentic.

Experimental

Infrared spectra were determined in KBr pellets on Beckman IR-5A unit. All melting points are uncorrected.

The key starting 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were obtained by oxidative cyclisation of aldehyde semicarbazones¹⁰.

N-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)triphenylimidophosphoranes(I) :

A well stirred suspension of dibromotriphenylphosphorane (1 m.mol) in 30 ml dry benzene was treated slowly (30 min) with a solution of aminooxadiazole (1 m.mol) and triethylamine (1 m.mol) in 30 ml dry benzene. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hr and then refluxed for four hrs. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was removed by filtration. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the residue crystallised from benzene.

Table 1 represents the physical and analytical data of (I).

TABLE 1—TRIPHENYLIMIDOPHOSPHORANES(I)

No.	R	m.p. °C	Formula	Microanalysis	
				Calcd. %N	Found
Ia	H	170-172	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₄ OP	9.97	9.85
Ib	<i>m</i> -Cl	188-190	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ OP	9.22	9.14
Ic	<i>p</i> -Cl	207-208	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ OP	9.22	9.32
Id	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	176-178	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ OP	9.65	9.53
Ie§	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O	200-201	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ P	9.31	9.18

§ The composition of Ia and Ie was also checked by analysis for phosphorus.

Ia, Calcd. P, 7.36 Found 7.50.

Ie, Calcd. P, 6.87 Found 7.00

Hydrolysis of *N*-(5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl)triphenylimidophosphoranes(I) :

Imidophosphoranes(I) (1 gm) was refluxed for three hours with dilute HCl (30 ml), then cooled and extracted with benzene. The benzene solution was washed with water and dried over sodium sulfate. Upon evaporation of benzene, triphenylphosphine oxide was obtained (70%), identified by mixed m.p. and comparison of the infrared with an authentic.

The parent aminooxadiazoles were obtained from the acidic solution by neutralisation with sodium hydroxide.

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Stereochemistry and Anti-inflammatory Activity of Carboxymethoximes of Ketones†

MAHAVIR PRASHAD, M. SETH and A. P. BHADURI*

Division of Medicinal Chemistry

and

R. C. SRIMAL

Division of Pharmacology, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

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DURING the course of an investigation of carboxymethoximes as anti-inflammatory agents, Dijk and Zwagemakers¹ reported the anti-inflammatory activity of a number of oxime ether derivatives. The observations concerning the stereochemistry and the anti-inflammatory activity of carboxymethoximes of ketones made in this laboratory are recorded in this communication.

Reaction of the oximes of various ketones with monochloroacetic acid in presence of sodium hydroxide in aqueous alcohol yielded the *o*-alkylated derivative as was evident from the fact that identical compounds were also obtained when the ketones were reacted with 2-(aminooxy)acetic acid hemihydrochloride (Fig. 1). The assignment of the

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